

DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING EMPATHY IN STUDENTS IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the didactic possibilities of developing empathy skills in students in children's literature classes. In the study, the processes of analyzing literary works, understanding the character of characters, and understanding the mental state of characters are highlighted as an important pedagogical factor in the formation of students' empathic thinking. Also, on the example of poetic and prose works of representatives of Uzbek children's literature, methodological approaches serving the development of empathy are shown. The research results show that the use of interactive methods in the organization of children's literature lessons serves the development of empathy, humanism, and socio-emotional competencies in students.*

Keywords: *empathy, children's literature, didactic possibilities, artistic analysis, socio-emotional education, pedagogical methods, student competence.*

In the current process of globalization, one of the important tasks in the education system is not only the provision of knowledge, but also ensuring the socio-emotional development of the individual. Especially in the process of training future teachers, the formation of empathy skills is becoming an urgent issue. Empathy expresses a person's ability to understand the emotional state of another person, to empathize with them, and to adhere to the principles of humanism in social relations.

Children's literature, with its artistic and aesthetic nature, system of images, and educational content, has a great influence on the development of empathy. In the process of reading a literary work, the reader or student feels the experiences of the characters, empathizes with their problems, and through this, human qualities are formed. In this regard, children's literature lessons have important didactic possibilities for the development of empathic thinking in

students. Children's literature differs from other literary trends in its artistic and aesthetic content, system of images, and strong educational direction. In works of this type, life events are depicted in a simple, understandable, and impressive artistic form. Through images close to the psyche of children, the authors artistically interpret such qualities as human relations, moral values, kindness, friendship, justice, and care. As a result, such works not only provide aesthetic pleasure, but also serve the spiritual and moral development of the individual. In particular, the emotional impact of artistic images directly affects the inner world of the reader or student. Feelings such as joy, anguish, surprise, fear, or hope, expressed through images, form a certain emotional experience in the reader's mind. In the process of reading literary works, the reader or student imagines the mental state of the hero of the work, tries to understand the events he is experiencing through inner feelings. This process transforms the reader not into a passive observer, but into an emotional participant in artistic reality. By understanding the hero's problems, decision-making processes, and emotional experiences, the reader, to a certain extent, puts himself in his place. This process serves the formation of empathic thinking. Empathy refers to a person's ability to understand another person's emotional state and empathize with them. In pedagogical and psychological research, empathy is assessed as an important factor in the social adaptation of a person, communicative culture, and the correct establishment of human relations.

Scientific research in the field of psychology and pedagogy shows that fiction has a significant positive influence on the emotional and intellectual development of a person. In the process of working with a literary text, the imagination, emotional perception, and reflexive thinking of the reader or student are activated. In particular, such processes as analyzing the mental state of the characters, evaluating their behavior, and expressing a personal attitude towards events serve the development of emotional thinking. And empathy, which is one of the main components of emotional intelligence, helps a person to establish effective communication with others, to ensure solidarity and mutual understanding in social relations. Another important feature of children's literature is that it expresses human values directly through artistic images. In this case, moral ideas are revealed not in the form of dry didactic advice, but through life events, images, and plots. As a result, the reader or student perceives moral ideas not as mandatory rules, but as life experience. For example, when ideas such as friendship, mutual assistance, compassion, and

careful attitude towards nature are expressed through artistic images, they are firmly established in the reader's emotional memory. This has a positive impact on the formation of a person's social and moral views. From this point of view, children's literature lessons are an important pedagogical tool for enriching students' emotional experience, developing their emotional sensitivity, and forming socio-emotional competencies. Especially in students studying in the pedagogical field, the development of empathy skills is of great importance for future professional activity. Because the teacher must be able to correctly understand the student's mental state, pay attention to their emotional needs, and create a sincere psychological environment in the learning process. In children's literature classes, such methodological approaches as the analysis of literary works, the discussion of the mental state of characters, and the evaluation of the actions of characters serve the development of empathetic thinking in students.

In the system of pedagogical higher education, children's literature classes serve not only the acquisition of literary knowledge, but also play an important role in the formation of students' spiritual and moral views, personal position, and pedagogical worldview. In the process of training future teachers, along with their professional competencies, the development of human qualities is also an important pedagogical task. In this regard, children's literature lessons are one of the effective educational tools that serve to form students' aesthetic taste, enrich their spiritual world, and develop thinking based on moral values.

In the process of studying literary works, students gain a deeper understanding of the essence of events by analyzing the plot of the work, the system of images, and the author's idea. In particular, the process of analyzing the actions of the characters, evaluating their decisions, and identifying the reasons for such decisions develops critical and reflexive thinking in students. In the process of evaluating the actions of the hero in a certain situation, students try to understand his mental state, which develops the ability to understand the feelings of another person. Thus, the process of working with a literary text activates not only the intellectual, but also the emotional thinking of students. One of the important features of children's literature is that moral ideas are expressed through real-life events and images. This allows the reader or student to have a deeper understanding of moral values. Such qualities as friendship, kindness, compassion, mutual assistance, honesty, and justice, reflected in the works, are described as important criteria of human relations. In the process of

familiarization with such ideas, students not only evaluate the actions of the characters, but also form their own personal attitude towards the events. This process serves the development of students' moral consciousness and the formation of a worldview based on human values. Also, in the process of reading and analyzing literary works, students try to understand the emotional experiences of the characters in various situations. By imagining such situations as the hero's joy, suffering, fear, or hope, the student enriches their emotional experience. This process plays an important role in the development of a sense of empathy and increases a person's sensitivity to the experiences of others. Empathy is an important component of social relations and plays an important role in ensuring mutual understanding, cooperation, and social harmony.

The formation of empathy skills is especially important in the process of pedagogical education. Because in the future, a specialist engaged in pedagogical activity must be able to correctly understand the emotional state of students, organize the educational process taking into account their individual characteristics. In children's literature classes, such methodological approaches as in-depth analysis of literary texts, discussion of the mental state of characters, and expression of personal opinion on events serve the development of students' empathic thinking. At the same time, discussions based on literary works also develop students' communicative culture. In the process of exchanging ideas about the content of the work, students learn to listen to the opinions of others, to respect different views, and to express their opinion in a reasonable way. This helps them develop not only empathy, but also social communication skills. As a result, children's literature lessons serve as an important didactic tool for enriching the spiritual world of students, forming their moral views, and developing their socio-emotional competencies. Such qualities as empathy, empathy, and humanism, formed in the process of studying works of art, are of great importance in the professional activity of future teachers. Therefore, the purposeful and effective use of the educational and didactic possibilities of children's literature lessons in the system of pedagogical higher education serves the formation of students as a comprehensively developed personality.

The didactic possibilities of developing empathy in children's literature lessons are manifested in several pedagogical processes. First of all, through the analysis of literary texts, students develop the ability to understand the mental state of the characters. In the process of analyzing the feelings of the hero of the

work, students try to determine the reasons for his actions, which develops empathetic thinking. Secondly, discussions organized on the basis of problematic questions encourage students to look at events from different perspectives. For example, by asking students questions about what decisions they would make in the hero's place, their emotional thinking is activated. Thirdly, through dramatization and role-playing, students gain a deeper sense of the character's state in a literary work. Such methods expand students' emotional experience and serve the development of empathy skills. Also, the use of interactive methods in children's literature lessons has a positive impact on the development of empathy. Group discussions, debates, creative tasks, and reflection processes encourage students to understand the content of a literary text more deeply. By analyzing the events depicted in a literary work and the experiences of the characters, students learn to listen to the opinions of others and treat them with respect. This serves the development of communicative culture and empathic relationships in students.

The results of scientific research show that regular work with fiction develops a person's emotional intelligence. And empathy, which is one of the important components of emotional intelligence, increases the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. Therefore, when organizing children's literature classes in pedagogical higher educational institutions, it is important to effectively use their educational and emotional capabilities. In this case, it is necessary to deeply analyze literary texts, organize discussions based on problem situations, and create opportunities for students to freely express their personal opinions.

In conclusion, children's literature lessons are an effective pedagogical tool with important didactic possibilities for developing empathy skills in students. In the process of studying literary works, students' emotional thinking is activated, they try to understand the emotional experiences of the characters of the work, to understand the feelings of people in various life situations. This process not only forms aesthetic taste in students, but also has a positive impact on their socio-emotional development. In the process of working with a literary text, students analyze the actions of the characters, evaluate their decisions, and express their attitude towards the events. As a result, they acquire such important qualities as understanding the experiences of others, empathizing with them, and valuing human relationships. Especially for students studying in the pedagogical field, the development of empathy skills is of great importance in future professional activity. Because the teacher must establish effective

communication with students, understand their psychological state, and create a comfortable and sincere environment in the educational process. Therefore, the systematic and purposeful use of methodological approaches aimed at the development of empathy in the organization of children's literature lessons in the system of pedagogical higher education is of great importance. This serves as an important factor in strengthening the professional competence of future teachers and increasing the overall effectiveness of the educational process.

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